

POLYMERIC RESINS AND THEIR POTENTIAL INTERACTIVITY WITH SOLID REINFORCEMENTS: THE HYDROGEN BOND

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ABSTRACT

In reinforced polymers technology it is of key importance the good adhesion between matrix resin and the reinforcement. Both parts of the interface play a role and contribute to the adequate adhesion. In the side of the resin, of organic character, functional groups dominate the adhesion capability of the polymeric part to the reinforcement.

Inverse Gas Chromatography, IGC, is a good tool to study surface sites of powders. In this paper three cured resins of common use in composites are studied under the perspective of their surface activity.

Traditionally, the main *reference set of probes* used in IGC at infinite dilution is the n-alkane series (R-H). The free energy of adsorption of the members of this series provides a significant value: *the free energy of adsorption of the CH₂ group*.

In this paper n-alcohol homologous series, ROH, are used as probes to obtain outstanding information of the surface characteristics.

The first result is *the free energy of adsorption of the OH group*, in close relation with the acid-basic character of the surface.

The second interesting result is the observation of the *anomalous free energy of adsorption of the lower members of the series*, which we think is closely related to the formation of hydrogen-bridge bonds.

Solid cured phenolic, furanic, cyanoester and PPS resins are studied, and their capability to form hydrogen-bridge bonds evaluated.

KEYWORDS: Solid polymers, Inverse Gas Chromatography, n-alcohol series, hydrogen-bridge bonding.

INTRODUCTION

Among the most widely used resins are the phenolics. This family of thermosetting polymers have a complete name of polyphenolformaldehyde and acronym for these resins is PF. The main functional groups in the polymer network are *aromatic rings, OH groups and alkyl chains*.

Furanic resins are the linear condensation products of furfuryl alcohol or other self- or co-condensates containing furan rings. The acid-catalysed self-condensation reaction leads to the formation of linear oligomers containing mainly *methylene and methylene-ether linked to furan-ring groups*.

Cyanate ester resins are rapidly expanding in the aerospace industry. They are formed by the reaction of corresponding phenols with cyanogen halides. The functional groups always present in their network are *aromatic rings, -OCN groups and alkyl radicals*.

Poly (*p*-phenylene sulfide), PPS, is classified as an engineering thermoplastic because it possesses a favourable combination of mechanical, electrical, thermal and flame-resistant properties. They are formed by reaction of *p*-dihalogenbenzene and sodium sulfide. The functional groups present in the network are *aromatic rings, -S- and -S-S- groups*

The functional groups present in the polymer network are the anchorage tools to adhere properly on the reinforcement surface. In these polymers hydrogen-bridge bonding plays an important role. We pay

particular attention to this in the study presented here. We should study the resin character in a non-cured or perhaps B stage to go to the real situation when reinforcement and matrix form the interface, but as in those stages the polymeric systems are dynamic, we choose to study stable cured resin powders under the assumption that functional groups, in the polymer are the same than in the intermediate B stage, which is not always strictly true.

Gas Chromatography is an easy technique of separation and/or identification of solutes in a mixture, based on the fact that, each solute has a *particular* interaction with the stationary phase, and therefore, the different solutes travel through the column, carried by an inert gas, at different rates. The solutes come out of the column separately and the retention volume, V_R , of each solute, depends on different parameters, among others, the nature of the stationary phase and the nature of the solute.

IGC takes advantage of this fact, by using a series of solutes (probes), of well known physicochemical characteristics. Introducing them into the column, and measuring their V_R , valuable information of the nature of the column can be obtained, being in this case the column material to be investigated.

Injecting a minimum vapour amount of solutes, in the limit of FID detector sensitivity, allows assuming that no solute-solute interactions take place, only solid-solute interactions occur. In these conditions, Henry's law can be applied and the proportion of adsorbed solute, and therefore the retention volume V_R , is practically independent of the probe concentration.¹⁻²

The retention volume (V_R) of a solute is related to standard variation of the free energy of adsorption according to

$$- \Delta G_A = R T \text{Ln } V_R + C \quad (1)$$

where C is a constant that depends on the reference state³, R is the gas constant and T is the column temperature in °K.

According to Fowkes⁴, the solid surface is a set of different accessible active sites of different nature and heterogeneous character. The surface energy, γ_s , is the sum of the free energy of all of those active sites. Generally, γ_s can be split in two components

$$\gamma_s = \gamma_s^d + \gamma_s^{sp} \quad (2)$$

where γ_s^d , or the London component of the free energy, is the sum of the free energy of those active sites non-polar, that can only interact with in-coming molecules, with dispersive interactions, and γ_s^{sp} , or the Specific component of the free energy, is the sum of surface free energy, of all other specific active sites of polar nature, with different character and intensity.

When injecting n-alkane in a column S, we obtain ΔG_{CH_2} (free energy of adsorption of a methylene group) from the slope of line obtained when plotting ΔG_A , versus number of carbon atoms.

where according to Fowkes's expression⁵

$$W_{CH_2 \text{ London}} = 2 (\gamma_s^d \gamma_{CH_2^d})^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

N-alcohols are, contrarily to hydrocarbons, *heterogeneous molecules*. The chain is of the same nature than hydrocarbons, and the hydroxyl group, a permanent dipole of amphoteric character.

We find that Voelkel et al.⁶ relate directly the hydrogen bonding interactions (I_{12h}) with the solubility parameters of n-alcohols compared with those of n-alkanes in some oligoethers, finding that these parameters decrease rapidly with the increasing length of the apolar hydrocarbon chain. The solubility parameters are determined by Voelkel et al.⁷ by inverse gas chromatography.

Similarly we consider that the work of adsorption of the lower members of n-alcohols provides a similar evidence of the presence of hydrogen bridge bonds between the solute and the solid surface in the column. We, propose in this paper to distinguish the acid-base type interaction of the -OH group, as an amphoteric

radical, from the particular hydrogen bridge interaction with those solids, like some liquid resins with appropriate functional groups.

The hydrogen bond⁸ is a term given to the secondary interaction between a hydrogen atom bound to an electronegative atom and another atom which is also generally electronegative and which has one or more lone pairs and can thus act as a base. A generalised representation of a hydrogen bond can be $X^{\delta-} \cdots H^{\delta+} \cdots Y^{\delta-}$. Main proton donors are N-H, O-H and F-H, and the most commonly encountered hydrogen bonds are $O^{\delta-} \cdots H^{\delta+} \cdots O$ and $N^{\delta-} \cdots H^{\delta+} \cdots N$. The acceptor atoms can be N, O, F, Cl, Br, I, S or P, but carbon never acts as an acceptor other than in certain π -systems like polarizable double bonds or aromatic ring systems. The energies of these bonds lie in the range 4-40 kJ/mol according to literature.

When injecting ROH series on columns filled with polymeric solids with functional groups such as those present in the resins that we study here, hydrogen-bridge bond interactions should be expected. We observe that the lower members of the series have an anomalous high retention and we propose in this paper that this effect is directly related to this type of bond.

EXPERIMENTAL

The instrument used is a Perkin Elmer Autosystem. The detector is flame ionisation (FID) in the highest sensitive range, in the limit of detection. The amount of probes injected is 0.01 to 50 μ l of gas, taken from the headspace of the vessels, to be sure of working at infinite dilution. The carrier gas is helium and the flow rates are in the range of 3 to 30 ml/min for each solid stationary phase studied.

Dead retention time, t_M , is calculated by mathematical fitting of expression

$$(t_E - A) = \exp(B + Cn) \quad (4)$$

Therefore for $n = 0$,

$$t_M = A + \exp B \quad (5)$$

which would be the retention time of an hypothetical n-alkane with 0 number of carbon atoms. The retention time of each member of the series of n- alkanes is

$$t_{Ri} = t_{Ei} - t_M \quad (6)$$

Cured Furanic (Fuy) and cured phenolic (Fe-1) resins of Bakelite Iberica S.A, cured cyanoester resin extracted from a carbon fibre prepreg of Fiberite and cured PPS resin extracted from a carbon fibre semipreg of Tencate Advanced Composites were studied. The formers were introduced in the column as grinded powder, the later was solvent-extracted from a prepreg and glass beads were impregnated with the extract. The beads were heated until a complete curing is achieved. Grinded polyethylene (1- 5 μ m diameter grain size) was used as reference material.

All materials were introduced in Teflon tubing of 1/4" or 1/8" outer diameter, V_R are *adjusted retention volumes*, calculated through

$$V_R = F_a (T_r/T_a) t_R \quad (7)$$

Where F_a is the carrier gas flow rate, measured at the column outlet at ambient pressure, and temperature (T_a), T_r is the reference temperature 25°C.

All probes injected for measurements are HPLC quality.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

POLYETHYLENE, PE, AS REFERENCE MATERIAL

The work of adsorption of any molecule can be expressed in different energy units. One of the most convenient is the before mentioned CH_2 index, (I_x) which is a slight modification of the well known Kóvats's index which value is independent of many variables like flow rate, column size, dead volume, % stationary phase, contact area, etc. I_x is only dependent on the probe characteristics, the characteristics of the stationary phase, and the temperature⁹.

By definition, the I_x value for n-alkane series *in any column and temperature* is **n** for $C_n H_{n+2}$

I_x value, for any other molecule, is the work of adsorption of that molecule divided by the work of adsorption of the methylene group *in the same column and temperature*.

The polar probes in PE have a work of adsorption that result in different retention volumes and therefore different retention indexes. We observe that these indexes, on polyethylene are almost non-temperature dependant. The mean values measured experimentally are

Table 1. I_x values of polar probes and n-alcohols on PE

Molecule	Average	Molecule	Average
Chloroform	6.18	Methanol	4.18
Acetone	4.78	Ethanol	4.48
Ethyl acetate	5.80	n-Propanol	5.31
Diethyl oxide	5.03	n-Butyl alcohol	6.28
Tetrahydrofuran	6.27	n-Pentyl alcohol	7.30
Acetonitrile	4.79	n-Hexyl alcohol	8.32
Methylene chloride	5.53	n-Heptyl alcohol	9.34
2-Propyl alcohol	4.69	OH group	2.26

I_x of the hydroxyl group is obtained from the I_x of all members of the series of n-alcohols on PE. In fig.1 we see the W_a of ROH molecules on polyethylene versus number of CH_2 in the molecule. We obtain a line parallel to the n-alkane's where the *intercept* corresponds to W_a^{OH} on PE. This value expressed in I_x is

$$I_x^{OH} \text{ on PE} = 2.26 \pm 0.08 \quad (8)$$

The interaction of the polar probes with polyethylene surface is a two-term magnitude: one accounting the London interaction of the unspecific part of the probe molecule, and the other accounting Debye interactions with the polar part of the probe molecule. The expression governing these interactions is not known, but we find experimentally an approximately linear correlation when plotting DN/AN^* versus I_x/AN^* of acetone, ethyl acetate, tetrahydrofuran, acetonitrile, 2-propyl alcohol, methanol and ethanol on polyethylene.

DN and AN numbers used here are those given by V. Gutmann¹⁰ F.L. Riddle Jr. and F.M. Fowkes¹¹ From the linear equation found *we recalculate DN/AN^* values*.

The linear relation shown in Fig.3 cannot be imputed to other than Debye interactions of polar probes with PE. Therefore we propose the following expression for these type of interactions

$$W_{aDebye}(\text{probe L}) = \gamma_{PE} * \gamma_L^{polar} \quad (9)$$

and

$$\gamma_L^{polar} = (AN + DN)_L \quad (10)$$

With the DN/AN corrected values, and expressions 9 and 10 we *calculate new AN and DN s for polar probes in index (on PE) energy units*. These are shown in table 2

Table 2. New values for AN^x and DN^x of polar probes, in index energy units on PE

Probe	DN/AN ^{10,11}	DN/AN* corrected	AN (index on PE)	DN (index on PE)
Chloroform	0	3.81	2.57	9.79
Acetone	6.80	6.23	1.32	8.23
Ethyl acetate	11.40	12.41	0.87	10.74
Diethyl ether	13.71	11.53	0.80	9.25
Tetrahydrofuran	40.00	39.80	0.31	12.24
Acetonitrile	3.00	3.41	2.17	7.41
Methylene chloride	0	4.67	1.95	9.10
Methanol	1.58	1.30	3.64	4.72
Ethanol	1.94	1.57	3.49	5.48
OH		1.01	2.25	2.28

HYDROGEN-BRIDGE BOND

Each alcohol will have, in contact with a heterogeneous surface, a complex mixture of works of interaction. The resulting is reflected in the retention volume $V_{R\ ROH_i}$. We consider this work of adhesion $W_{a\ ROH_i}$ to be the result of adding the work of adhesion of the chain and the hydroxyl group, therefore

$$W_{a\ ROH_i} = W_{a\ R_i} + W_{a\ OH_i} \quad (11)$$

The alkyl chain of n-alcohols behaves as the hydrocarbon chain and we obtain also a line when plotting $R\ T\ Ln\ V_R$ of ROH_i versus number of CH₂ groups. From the slope of this line on S we can obtain $W_{a\ CH_2ROH}$, and

$$W_{a\ R_i} = n * (W_{a\ CH_2ROH}) \quad (12)$$

where n is the number of CH₂ groups in -R.

Eqs. 11 and 12 allow to calculate $W_{a\ OH_i}$ for all members of ROH series.

The hydroxyl group, -OH, has no possibility of London-type interactions and its work of adsorption can be split in two terms

$$W_{a\ OH_i} = W_{a\ OH_i\ Debye} + W_{a\ OH_i\ Keesom} \quad (13)$$

the first term enclosing the Debye interaction of the dipole -OH with the dispersive component of the solid surface according to Gutiérrez's proposal¹²

$$W_{a\ OH\ Debye} = \gamma_S^d (AN_{OH} + DN_{OH}) \quad (14)$$

and the second term enclosing the acid-base interaction of the -OH with the acid and basic sites of the solid surface. Accepting the simplest equation used in the literature¹³

$$W_{a\ OH_i\ Keesom} = K_{a\ S} * DN_{OH} + K_{b\ S} * AN_{OH} \quad (15)$$

When injecting ROH members in columns with solid resins we observe, as mentioned before, retention patterns like those shown in fig. 1

Fig. 1. Retention of ROH members on solid organic resins, in kJ/mol

In this figure we can compare the interaction of the n-alcohols with PE, as reference material, and the interaction of that homologous series with different solid resins.

We observe that the slope of the alkyl chain, compared with that of n-alkanes, is not the same in all the solid resins. In PE we know that is slightly higher than 1, while that of n-alkanes is by definition 1. The slope < 1 means a certain type of *orientation* of the molecules when travelling through the column. A higher affinity of the -OH group with the surface active sites will lead to a lower slope in the chain and at the same time a higher -OH interaction compared with the interaction of the CH₂ group. In a sense this is a measure of the polarity of the surface. We can observe that the phenolic and PPS resins are clearly more polar than the rest. In table 3 we show these slope values

Table 3. Wa CH₂ in Ix, of the alkyl chain of alkanes and alcohols on several resins

Wa CH ₂ in Ix	Polyethylene	Cyano 45°	Furanic 40°	PPS 80°	Phenolic 60°
n-alkanes	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
n-alcohols	1.009	0.997	0.983	0.7405	0.7383

We also observe different adsorption patterns in the lower members of the ROH molecules.

We can say, that in polyethylene, where hydrogen-bridge bond is not possible, the *inductive effect* of the chain produces, in methanol, an increase of the -OH group adsorption of 0.90 Ix_{PE} units caused by the higher AN* value of this alcohol if compared with higher members of the series, in ethanol this increase is 0.20 Ix_{PE} units, 0.02 Ix_{PE} units in n-propanol and practically 0 in the rest of the members of the series.

An alkyl chain, C₃-C₂-C₁-X, linked to atom with higher electron affinity than C, will cause a shift of the σ electrons of the covalent bond towards the atom X, causing a slight positive charge in the C₁ atom, which in turn will attract to itself the σ electrons of the neighbouring C₂-C₁ bond, effect that will propagate along the chain. This displacement of electrons is permanent and decreases drastically when increasing the distance to the focus. In practice can be neglected from the second carbon atom on¹⁴. This electron shift will weaken the O-H bond and consequently an increase in AN value of methanol should be observed while there is no reason for a change in DN value of the molecule. Values of AN and DN given in the literature for methanol, ethanol and butanol are in table 4 and are in agreement with this hypothesis.

Table 4. AN and DN values of n-alcohols reported in the literature.

Molecule	AN* ¹⁵ kcal/mol	DN ¹⁶ kcal/mol
Methanol	12.0	19.0
Ethanol	10.3	20.0
n-Butanol	9.1	
Water	15.1	18.0

The hydrogen bridge bond provokes the same electron shift in the O-H bond, but the origin is external to the alcohol molecule from certain basic sites of the solid surface. An extra-interaction of the type acid-base occurs and a way to measure the potentiality of a surface to form this type of bond is the consideration of this extra-interaction.

In fig. 2 we can observe the extra-retention of lower members of the series compared with the retention line that form the higher members of n-alcohol series. Extrapolation of these lines to n°C=0, drawing a line ethanol-methanol, gives a new extra-Wa OH adsorption value that should reflect the potentiality of hydrogen bond interaction. As by definition polyethylene has no potentiality at all, the magnitude that we propose is the difference of these extra-WaOH values and the value found in PE.

Fig. 2. Extra-retention of ROH lower members on solid organic resins, in kJ/mol

The Wa OH measured from the extrapolation to n° of C = 0 in higher member of the ROH series is called OH a-b, and the Wa OH measured from extrapolation of methanol-ethanol line to n° of C = 0, subtracted this value on polyethylene, is called OH h-bridge. In table 5 we show the measured data on several solid resins

Table 5. Wa calculated for OH, for acid-base and hydrogen bridge interactions

Material	OH a-b kJ/mol	OH h-bridge kJ/mol
Polyethylene 70°	6.55	0
Cyanoester 45°	13.51	16.70
Furanic 70°	12.43	6.54
PPS 80°	11.41	5.61
Phenolic 60°	23.22	16.32

As can be observed, these two Wa OH values have no relation, as Ka and Kb values of these solid surfaces have not necessarily direct relation with these extra-WaOH values which we think in relation with hydrogen bonding. On the contrary, Wa OH a-b values show a quite good correlation with calculated Kb values of the solid resins as shown in fig.3.

Fig. 3. Correlation of Wa OH a-b values on cured organic resins and K_b s, in kJ/mol

Of the four cured resins studied we can say that

a) Regarding acid-base surface activity the high-to-low order is

Phenolic > Cyanoester > Furanic > PPS

b) Regarding hydrogen bonding surface activity the high-to-low order is

Cyanoester > Phenolic > Furanic > PPS

CONCLUSION

1. We can see the presence of hydrogen-bridge bonding by injecting n-alcohols on the solid surface of resins with proton acceptor groups in their composition.
2. We propose a method to distinguish acid-base interaction of the amphoteric hydroxyl group from other specific interactions
3. We propose a method to estimate the potential interactivity of the cured solid resin with the hydroxyl group through hydrogen bridge bonding.
4. The projection of these results to choose the best processing resin in the manufacturing of reinforced composites is noted.

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